

THE ROLE OF SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS SCHOOL'S COMPETENCE AND LEARNER'S ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 2

Pages: 250-265

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2347

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13743617

Manuscript Accepted: 07-27-2024

The Role of School-Based Management Practices Towards School's Competence and Learner's Academic Performance

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Abstract

This study determined the role of school-based management practices towards teacher's competence and learners' academic performance. This study utilized a quantitative survey for a descriptive-correlational research methodology. The respondents of this study were the 105 public school teachers and 269 Grade 6 learners in 7 different schools in Maitum East District namely: Malalag Central Elementary School, Maitum Elementary School, Sison Elementary School Pangi Elementary School, Kipakuda Elementary School, Linao Elementary School, Kiayap Elementary School. Based on the results, the extent of school-based management was manifested most of the time in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, and accountability and continuous improvement, while manifested occasionally in terms of management and resources. Moreover, the level of school competence was very high in terms of transparency and student's learning outcome, while high in terms of school heads leadership and continuous improvement. Further, majority of the Grade 6 learners obtained a satisfactory academic performance. Furthermore, there was significant relationship between school-based management practices and school competence. Additionally, there was significant relationship between school-based management practices and academic performance of learners. Lastly, multiple linear regression analysis shows that there was a significant relationship between school-based management practices and school competence, and school-based management practices and academic performance of learners.

Keywords: *educational management, school-based management practices, teacher's competence, academic performance, qualitative research, philippines*

Introduction

Global academic issues include access to quality education, social justice, mental health, and technology's impact. Inadequate education perpetuates poverty; discrimination hampers equity, and mental health issues affect performance and well-being. Technological advancements demand resource access. Solutions require a comprehensive approach: social justice, mental health support, quality education, and keeping up with technology for student preparation (Vare et al., 2019).

Moreover, the academic life of learners is crucial for personal growth and societal success. Education equips learners with knowledge, skills, and competencies for their development and contribution to society. Quality education breaks poverty cycles and promotes social mobility, while equity addresses social and economic inequalities. Prioritizing student well-being improves academic outcomes and fosters resilience. Keeping up with technology and providing resources prepares learners for the evolving job market. The significance of learners' academic lives cannot be overstated for personal and societal growth (Kraft & Blazar, 2018).

In the Philippines, learners face challenges in their academic life, including limited access to quality education, insufficient funding, inadequate facilities, lack of teacher training, and social justice issues. Learners in remote or underprivileged areas lack educational opportunities, perpetuating poverty cycles. Inadequate government funding leads to a need for more essential resources like textbooks and classrooms. Insufficient teacher training impacts education quality. Discrimination and unequal resource distribution create equity issues. To address these issues, a comprehensive strategy includes social justice campaigns, more financing, better facilities, and continual teacher preparation for high-quality instruction (Brandt et al., 2019; Niati et al., 2021; Park et al., 2018).

On the other hand, global challenges in school competence hinder the quality of education and academic performance worldwide. Issues include inadequate funding, overcrowded classrooms, outdated facilities, and limited access to modern learning tools. Educational disparities among different socioeconomic groups perpetuate inequality, and the lack of well-trained teachers and professional development hampers effective instruction. Standardized testing and rote learning may limit critical thinking. Solving these problems requires collaboration among governments, policymakers, educators, and communities to establish fair, innovative, and inclusive educational systems that nurture students' abilities and enhance global competitiveness (Kim et al., 2019; MacCann et al., 2020; Salman et al., 2020).

Moreover, identified learners in the Maitum District suffer from poor academic life. Learners need help developing essential skills and knowledge for personal and professional success. It can hinder their ability to secure stable employment, contribute to economic growth, and escape poverty. As a public school teacher, school-based management practices have the potential to create more student-centered and effective learning environments that better prepare learners for success in the rapidly changing world.

There is an urgent need to research the role of school-based management practices in shaping learners' competence and academic life. With the evolving education landscape, understanding how school-based management practices influence student outcomes is crucial

for effective educational reform and policymaking. Research in this area can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of decentralizing decision-making, involving stakeholders, and promoting collaboration within schools. It can shed light on the impact of such practices on student achievement, engagement, and overall academic performance. Additionally, investigating the relationship between school-based management and learner competence can help identify best practices and inform strategies for improving educational quality, equity, and student success. Given the urgency to enhance educational systems worldwide, researching school-based management practices is imperative for evidence-based decision-making and creating optimal learning environments for all learners.

Hence, the researcher conducted this study to determine the level of school-based training programs and the relationship between schools' competence and learners' academic performance in Maitum East Districts for the school year 2022-2023. The findings of this study could be valuable for policymakers, educators, and school administrators to understand the importance of school competence and the potential impact of training programs on students' academic performance. A positive relationship between school competence and academic performance could provide insights into the significance of investing in professional development and improving school resources to enhance educational outcomes.

Research Objectives

This study determined the role of school-based management practices in a school's competence and learners' academic performance. Specifically, the following objectives were formulated:

1. To determine the extent of school-based management practices in terms of:
 - 1.1. leadership and governance;
 - 1.2. curriculum and learning;
 - 1.3. accountability and continuous improvement; and
 - 1.4. management and resources.
2. To determine the level of school competence in terms of:
 - 2.1. school heads leadership;
 - 2.2. transparency;
 - 2.3. continuous improvement; and
 - 2.4. student learning outcomes.
3. To determine the level of academic performance of learners.
4. To determine the significance of the relationship between:
 - 4.1. school-based management practices and school's competence; and
 - 4.2. school-based management practices and academic performance of learners.
5. To determine which domains of school-based management practices predict learners' school competence and academic performance.

Methodology

This section discusses the research design, the research locale, the respondents, the research instrument, the research procedure for gathering the data, and the statistical treatment of data used in this study.

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, non-experimental approach utilizing a descriptive-correlational survey design. A quantitative approach is used to comprehend and explain the world around them, making qualitative research methods the oldest of any scientific procedures. Several methods are used in quantitative research design to examine social phenomena systematically using statistical or numerical data. Due to this reliance on measurement and the presumption that the phenomena under study can be quantified, quantitative research is measurement-based. It seeks to validate the measurements and look for patterns and correlations in the data (Habib, 2021).

Moreover, in quantitative research, closed-ended questions are frequently preferred. Respondents must be given a predetermined list of options to provide in-depth, open-ended responses. This design ensures that the quantitative research process is much more effective than if open-ended questions of the qualitative type were used. It is more effective because it eliminates the need for the time-consuming task of coding a sizable number of open-ended responses. However, when appropriate, the quantitative research design frequently permits the inclusion of an "Other" category in the list of possible answers to questions. As a result, respondents who do not directly fit into the major categories can still have their accurate responses recorded and used to analyze the research findings (Rahman, 2020).

Similarly, quantitative research design aims to gather and generalize numerical data to various populations. Before data collection, every detail in this design is painstakingly and precisely prepared, and the researcher has a clearly stated research question to which objective solutions are sought. Data examples include statistics and numerical data. A project can be used to look into causal linkages, forecast results, or generalize ideas more broadly (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020).

On the other hand, if determining the effect or relationship between the variables is the study's primary objective, then a descriptive-correlational survey design is the most appropriate method. Because the study's main objective was to ascertain whether there was a link between parental engagement, work satisfaction, and the learners' academic progress, the researcher employed a quantitative approach. Moreover, quantitative research designs often exhibit a deterministic philosophy based on the post-positivist paradigm or school of thought. Post-positivists investigate causes and the interactions and effects of various causes on outcomes. The post-positivist paradigm embraces the idea that reality can be discovered, albeit imperfectly and in a probabilistic sense. The approach is typically deductive, where most ideas or concepts are reduced to variables, and the relationship between or among them is tested. The knowledge that results is based on meticulous observation, measurement, and interpretation of objective reality (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019; Uchihara et al., 2019).

Moreover, the descriptive-correlation study approach shows correlations and conditions that exist and those that do not, describing and interpreting the world as it is. It is also a fact-finding study that enables the researcher to examine participants' traits, actions, and experiences. A particular kind of research design called a correlational study looks at the connections between two or more variables. A non-experimental research method known as correlational analysis allows researchers to measure two variables, comprehend and assess their statistical relationship, and do so without the influence of any other variable. No variables are altered or subject to the experimenter's control because correlational studies are not experimenting (Seeram, 2019).

In addition, a survey is a research methodology used to obtain information from a sample group to identify trends, develop new perspectives, and draw conclusions about a more prominent target population. Generally, surveys use structured questions to collect data, either quantitatively or qualitatively and can be conducted online, over the phone, by mail, or in person. Surveys are utilized in various sectors and on various subjects, such as public opinion polls, academics, market research, and social sciences.

A survey aims to gather information that can be examined and evaluated to learn more about the target population's attitudes, beliefs, actions, preferences, and traits. Surveys provide a systematic and efficient way to gather information, allowing researchers to draw conclusions and make informed decisions based on the collected data.

Participants

The respondents of this study were the 82 public school teachers and 161 Grade 6 learners from 7 different schools in Maitum East District. There were 33 teachers and 60 learners from Malalag Central Elementary School, 14 teachers and 34 learners from Maitum Elementary School, eight teachers and 16 learners from Sison Elementary School, seven teachers and 16 learners from Pangl Elementary School, seven teachers and 12 learners from Kipakuda Elementary School, seven teachers and 12 learners from Linao Elementary School, and seven teachers and 11 learners from Kiayap Elementary School.

The researcher utilized Slovin's formula to get the desired population for the teachers and learners. Only 82 teachers were the final respondents from 105 teacher-respondents, while only 161 learners were the final respondents from the 269 learner-respondents. Slovin's formula is a statistical method used to calculate the sample size needed for a survey or study based on the population being studied and the desired level of precision (Tejada & Punzalan, 2012). The table below shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

Schools	Number of Respondents			
	Teachers		Learners	
	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>
Malalag Central Elementary School	41	33	100	60
Maitum Elementary School	18	14	56	34
Sison Elementary School	10	8	27	16
Pangl Elementary School	9	7	26	16
Kipakuda Elementary School	9	7	21	12
Linao Elementary School	9	7	21	12
Kiayap Elementary School	9	7	18	11
TOTAL	105	82	269	161

Data Collection

To pursue this study, the researcher used the following procedures to gather data based on Igwenagu's (2016) book "Fundamental of Research Methodology and Data Collection." First, the researcher requested approval from the Graduate School and Ethics and Review Committee. After the request was granted, the researcher went to the Division of Sarangani's Schools Division Office and requested authorization to carry out the study from the office of the Superintendent of Schools. Fourth, the researcher prepared for reproducing the questionnaires according to the number of target respondents. After reproducing the questionnaire, the researcher personally explained the Informed Consent Form (ICF) and administered the questionnaire to the respondents.

They were given ample time to complete the questionnaires. Sixth, while retrieving questionnaires, the researcher checked if the participants had accomplished all the items. Finally, the completed questionnaires were summarized, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

Ethical Considerations

For this quantitative study, a critical ethical factor has specific ramifications. These problems and worries can primarily result from the approach used in this study. The ethical considerations in this research was concerned in the proper conduct of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. The RMMC Ethics and Review Committee's requirements for ethical consideration was adhered to in this study, especially when it pertained to the population and data, including but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The respondents were allowed to participate without any plan of repercussion, reparations, or loss of benefits. Therefore, after discussing the study's purpose and benefits, the respondents' rights to provide the body of knowledge were carefully measured and foresighted. The respondents of this study were not coerced into taking part. If people got uncomfortable while participating in the study, they were allowed to withdraw.

Privacy and confidentiality. According to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which upholds the fundamental human right to privacy, respondents have a right to privacy that cannot be infringed upon without the respondents' informed agreement. Allowing respondents to omit their names from the survey questionnaire is one technique to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. Additionally, secrecy and privacy were achieved by withholding the informants' demographic information, such as age, gender, occupation, and medical condition. As a result, their identity was kept private for security reasons. Their answers to the survey questionnaire were kept private and treated as such.

Informed consent process. The prospective research respondents were fully informed about the research's objectives, methods, and benefits as comprehensively as possible within the framework of the study. Each respondent's written consent was obtained, indicating that their participation was asked voluntarily. The respondents signed the informed consent form stating they willingly consented to participate in the study. Since the respondents were consenting adults, asking for parents' consent was not necessary. The respondents' identities were not mentioned on the survey form, and their responses were kept private. The participants knew they could withdraw from participating in the study anytime.

Furthermore, any data the researcher gathered was protected, and releasing any information would follow a strict informed consent process. The participants could control their personal information to lessen their fear that the data or information would be used in any other unintended manner.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. The researcher explained the study's purpose for further inference and understanding of its essence so that the respondents could understand it. The researcher gave the rationale of the study and its significance.

Risks. The research was conducted to determine an acceptable positive benefit-risk ratio. This study's need to protect the participants from significant harm is equally essential. Therefore, the study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the respondents were not harmed since their identities were held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. The researcher needed to ensure the respondents were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. The researcher answered the survey questionnaire and confirmed that the respondents did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. This research study was significant in many aspects to the following beneficiaries: The global significance of school-based management practices in shaping a school's competence and the academic life of learners cannot be overstated. As education systems face diverse challenges across different countries and regions, empowering schools with decision-making authority and involving stakeholders in management processes have emerged as crucial strategies for driving educational improvement. The result of the study may serve as a baseline for the school administrators to guide the administrators in formulating policies suited to the needs of the school community. The school's needs in storing information go through various changes, requiring the institution to re-examine its processes and workflows and whether they are aligned with the school's policies. Thus, each function must be checked to identify its information needs and review how to manage the information.

Furthermore, the survey result may serve as a basis for teachers in determining educational activities for fast and efficient public service in the different schools in Maitum Districts Evaluation of Teaching Performance questionnaire (CEID). Teachers may be helped in managing the data on actual dropouts to be utilized in planning. The results may also suggest actions or measures to address the limitations or weaknesses of DepEd programs to be used in the school's plan adjustments. The study results can serve as a vehicle for the learners to efficiently cater to their needs by immediately responding to their weaknesses. The results may also recommend new policies and enhancements in DepEd measures and systems for keeping school-age children. With this, plan adjustments may be maximized. The result of the study may be helpful for the present researcher to impart his findings to all the teachers in the Maitum District. There is also hope that other districts would utilize the results of this study within the division, especially in making decisions for improving the school systems and processes.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the research had misinterpreted someone else's work. Grammarly and other plagiarism detection technologies were applied to it. It would help if one has moral traits and ideals linked to excellent character and integrity to be a researcher. To produce a trustworthy research report, the researcher also has to be more knowledgeable about the concept of plagiarism.

Fabrication. The report had no hint or evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. Instead, the investigator utilized and incorporated ideas associated with the data and additional inferential notions.

Falsification. There was no indication that the study overstated or exaggerated anything or deliberately falsified the data to meet a model or theoretical assumption. Furthermore, this study needed to follow the guidelines for data manipulation, which included making claims based on incomplete information or omitting crucial elements, as well as using materials, equipment, or techniques that might deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study had no trace of conflicts of interest, such as the disclosure of COI, which is a collection of circumstances under which professional judgment regarding primary claims like participants' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by a secondary interest such as financial or academic gains or recognitions. In addition, the respondents were not coerced into participating in the survey by the researcher, who had no authority or influence over them.

Deceit. There was no evidence that the study misled the respondents about potential risks. The rights of everybody who participated in an investigation were fiercely protected, especially if they had completed higher education. Therefore, reasonable and suitable standards were followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The study's researcher adhered to protocol. Once the panelists, adviser, and committee of the RMMCERC approved, the researcher wrote an official letter to the division superintendent of the school requesting permission to perform the study. Following this, the researcher composed an official letter and attached the school's division superintendent's endorsed letter to the district supervisor and principal of the participating schools in the study. The public elementary school teachers and Grade 6 learners who were part of the study were oriented before administering the survey questionnaire.

Results

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered in the study.

3.1. The Extent of School-Based Management Practices

Table 1 presents the data on the extent of school-based management practices in terms of leadership and governance. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Based on the data, the findings indicated that school-based management practices in leadership and governance were manifested most of the time, with a mean score of 3.7. It suggests that these practices are consistently manifested in the school. The collaborative development of the School Improvement Plan (SIP) by the school and community stakeholders received a relatively high mean score of 4.0, indicating a solid collaborative effort. Additionally, as seen by a mean score of 3.7, a network of leadership and governance directs the educational system to fulfill its shared vision, mission, and objectives while exhibiting responsiveness and relevance to the context of diversity.

Further, with an average score of 3.6, the school exhibits a clear organizational structure, work arrangements that support shared leadership and governance, and a definition of the roles and duties of stakeholders. EA leadership network facilitates effective communication, connecting school and community leaders for informed decision-making and problem-solving, with a mean score of 3.8. Additionally, a long-term program in place to address the training and development needs of the school and community leaders, garnered an average score of 3.6.

Table 2. *The Extent of School-Based Management Practices in terms of Leadership and Governance*

<i>Leadership and Governance</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
The Development Plan (e.g., SIP) was developed collaboratively by the school and community stakeholders.	4.0	Often
The education system is guided by a network of leadership and governance to fulfill its shared vision, mission and objectives, enabling it to be relevant and adaptable to the diverse setting.	3.7	Often
The school has a well-defined structure and procedures that encourage shared governance and leadership while defining the roles and duties of all parties involved.	3.6	Often
A leadership network helps school and community leaders communicate with one another, facilitating well-informed decision-making and resolving issues related to learning that affect the school and the community.	3.8	Often
A long term program is meeting the training and development demands of community and school leaders.	3.6	Often
Total	3.7	Often

Table 3 presents the data on the extent of school-based management practices regarding curriculum and learning, management and resources, accountability, and continuous improvement. The extent of school-based management practices in curriculum and learning was manifested most of the time, with a mean score of 3.8. These practices are manifested most of the time in the school. With an average score of 3.5, the curriculum shows that it is sensitive to the requirements of all kinds of students in the school community. Moreover, the implemented curriculum is localized to ensure its relevance and applicability to the learners' lives in the community, as reflected by a mean score of 3.9.

Further, developing methods and materials for fostering creative thinking and problem-solving involves a representative group of school and community stakeholders, showcased a high mean score of 4.1. With a mean score of 3.8, the community routinely and cooperatively checked the learning systems using the necessary instruments to support the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community. Continuous review and improvement of assessment tools for teaching and learning are carried out, with assessment results contextualized to the learner and local situation and attaining relevant life skills, scored an average of 3.6.

Furthermore, teachers, administrators, and community members who serve as learning managers and facilitators play a crucial role in fostering attitudes and environments that protect and support all children. By consistently exhibiting behavior that aligns with the organization's vision, purpose, and objectives, they create a safe and nurturing atmosphere conducive to learning and development. Their efforts were highly effective, as reflected in the impressive mean score of 4.1, indicating a strong adherence to these principles and a positive impact on the school community. This approach was marked by a commitment to inclusivity and cultivating a sense of belonging within the learning community, fostering a supportive and collaborative atmosphere. The achievement of a mean score of 4.0 consistently highlighted the effectiveness of these efforts, indicating participant pleasure and the techniques' ability to produce the desired results.

Table 3. *The Extent of School-Based Management Practices in terms of Curriculum and Learning*

<i>Leadership and Governance</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
The curriculum considers the demands of every kind of student in the school.	3.5	Often
The curriculum is applied locally to give learners a deeper understanding and make it more relevant to community life.	3.9	Often
Creative thinking and problem-solving skills are developed through techniques and materials created by a representative group of community and school stakeholders.	4.1	Often
To guarantee the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community, the community frequently and cooperatively uses suitable instruments to monitor the learning systems.	3.8	Often
Developing appropriate assessment instruments for education is an ongoing process involving evaluation and improvement. Assessment outcomes are then contextualized to the learner, the local environment, and the acquisition of pertinent life skills.	3.6	Often
Teachers, Administrators, and Community members who serve as learning managers and facilitators foster attitudes and settings that safeguard all children and exhibit conduct in line with the organization's vision, purpose and objectives.	4.0	Often
Resources and methods are entertaining, safe, inclusive, accessible, learner and community friendly, and designed to foster the growth of self-directed learners. Students possess the fundamental information, abilities and morals needed to take ownership of their education.		
Total	3.8	Often

Table 4 presents the data on the extent of school-based management practices regarding accountability and continuous improvement. The extent of school-based management practices in terms of accountability and continuous improvement was manifested most of the time, as shown in the mean of 3.6. The roles and responsibilities of accountable individuals and collective bodies are clearly defined and agreed upon by the community stakeholders, with an average score of 3.5. The achievement of goals is recognized through a collaboratively developed performance accountability system, and any gaps identified are addressed through appropriate action, scored an average of 3.7.

Moreover, the community-owned accountability system continuously evolves to meet changing learning needs, averaged a score of 3.6. Collaborative development of assessment tools and criteria promotes inclusivity, scored 3.6 on average. Regular participatory assessments, also averaged 3.5, empower the community to evaluate performance, provide feedback, and make necessary adjustments to the plan.

Table 4. *The Extent of School-Based Management Practices in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement*

<i>Accountability and Continuous Improvement</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
The roles and obligations of the responsible individual or parties and group are well-defined and established by the community's stakeholders.	3.5	Often
A performance accountability system designed collectively recognizes target achievement and any gaps are filled by action.	3.7	Often
The accountability system is owned by the community and continuously enhances to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the community's emerging learning needs and demands.	3.6	Often
The procedures, information gathering and validation methods, accountability evaluation criteria and instruments, and feedback system are all-inclusive. Cooperatively designed, and approved.	3.6	Often
The community participates in participatory performance assessment regularly. The assessment results and lessons learned serve as the basis for feedback, technical assistance, recognition, and plan adjustment.	3.5	Often
Total	3.6	Often

Table 5 presents data on the extent of school-based management practices in terms of management and resources. The data revealed that the extent of school-based management practices in terms of management and resources was occasionally manifested, as shown its the mean of 3.4. The data reveals collaborative efforts in resource management, including regular resource inventory conducted by

learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders for resource allocation and mobilization, with an average score of 3.2.

Additionally, a regular dialogue for inclusive planning and resource programming engages stakeholders, supporting the implementation of community education plans, scoring a mean of 3.5. However, there is room for improvement in the mobilization and management of resources, aiming for collective and judicious practices that prioritize transparency, effectiveness, and efficiency, as reflected in a score of 3.4. Regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes for resource management should be collaboratively developed and implemented by learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders, with an average score of 3.3.

The accountability system is deeply integrated into the concept of community ownership, making it a collective responsibility rather than a top-down mandate. This system undergoes continuous refinement to remain responsive to the ever-changing educational landscape, ensuring that it adapts to new challenges and opportunities. Despite its complexity, the system's effectiveness is evident in its average score of 3.6, reflecting a solid performance and a recognition of the ongoing efforts to enhance its responsiveness and impact.

Table 5. *The Extent of School-Based Management Practices in terms of Management and Resources*

<i>Management and Resources</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
Learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders collaboratively undertake regular resource inventory as the basis for resource allocation and mobilization.	3.2	Sometimes
An accessible and inclusive regular dialogue for planning and resource programming continuously engages stakeholders and supports the implementation of community education plans.	3.5	Often
Transparency, efficacy and efficiency characterize the collaborative and prudent mobilization and management of resources.	3.4	Sometimes
The learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders collaboratively develop an implement regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes for resource management.	3.3	Sometimes
A system manages the network and linkages, strengthening and sustaining partnerships to improve resource management.	3.6	Often
Total	3.4	Sometimes

Table 6 summarized the results of a study on various educational indicators, showing their mean scores and corresponding descriptive frequencies. The indicators include Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Learning, Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and Management and Resources, each rated on a scale. Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Learning, and Accountability and Continuous Improvement garnered mean scores of 3.7, 3.8, and 3.6, respectively, indicating they are "Often" present or practiced. Management and Resources had a slightly lower mean score of 3.4, described as occurring "Sometimes." These results are based on responses from 82 participants.

Table 6. *Summary of Results*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
Leadership and Governance	3.7	Often
Curriculum and Learning	3.8	Often
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	3.6	Often
Management and Resources	3.4	Sometimes

3.2. The Level of School Competence in terms of School Heads Leadership, Transparency, Continuous Improvement, and Student Learning Outcomes

Table 7 presents the level of school competence regarding school heads' leadership. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Based on the data analysis, the findings indicated that the level of school competence in school heads' leadership was high, as reflected by a mean score of 4.3, which implies that they perform beyond what is expected of them. It suggests that school leaders are actively engaged in their roles and responsibilities. They demonstrated a clear mission, vision, and goals for the school, received a high average score of 4.6, indicating strong alignment and agreement among stakeholders. School leaders effectively assisted teachers with work problems, scored an average of 4.3, demonstrated their supportive and proactive approach to addressing challenges.

Relatively, they also showed openness to suggestions from teachers regarding policies and plans, with an average score of 4.4, emphasizing their collaborative and inclusive leadership style. Establishing a good linkage with the community is another strength of school leader, as indicated by a mean score of 3.9, highlighting their efforts to foster positive relationships and engagement beyond the school. Additionally, school leaders prioritize the smooth operation of the school, scored an average of 4.1, showcased their commitment to maintain a conducive learning environment.

Table 7. *The Level of School Competence in terms of School Heads Leadership*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
School leaders have a mission, vision, and goal for the school.	4.6	Very High
School leaders assist teachers in dealing with work problems.	4.3	High
School leaders accept suggestions from the teachers about the policies and plans.	4.4	High
School leaders establish good linkage with the community.	3.9	High

School leaders look for excellent school operations.	4.1	High
Total	4.3	High

In Table 8, the findings indicated a high level of school competence in transparency, with a mean score of 4.5, implying that they performed excellently. It signified strong agreement among respondents that schools prioritize transparency and accountability in education, scored an impressive average of 4.8. Schools recognized the importance of relevant data in encouraging stakeholders to actively participate in school accountability, received an average score of 4.6 and highlighted their commitment to data-driven decision-making.

Furthermore, schools strove to maintain transparency in their operations, particularly in using funds, including MOOE, IGP, and other financial transactions, scored an average of 4.5. It demonstrated their commitment to ensuring that financial processes are clear and accessible to stakeholders. Schools actively involved stakeholders in the planning and utilizing of school resources, as indicated by a mean score of 4.3, which emphasized their inclusive approach to resource management. Moreover, schools placed importance on properly auditing and liquidating the downloaded school budget, scored an average of 4.5, which signified their commitment to accountability and responsible financial management.

Table 8. *The Level of School Competence in terms of Transparency*

<i>Transparency</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
School provides public access to informatuon and accountability in education.	4.8	Very High
School prioritize relevant data to encourage participation in school accountability.	4.6	Very High
Schools should be transparent in MOOE, IGP, and other financial transactions.	4.5	Very High
Schools involve stakeholders in the planning and utiization of school resources.	4.3	High
Schools have proper auditing and liquidation of the download school budget.	4.5	Very High
Total	4.5	Very High

In 8, schools demonstrated a high level of competence in continuous improvement, with an average score of 3.7, which implies that they performed beyond what was expected of them. They agreed that schools prioritize framing and communicating broad goals for school improvement, indicating a commitment to growth and progress. Schools also actively provided continuous improvement initiatives for the teaching-learning process, scored an average of 3.7, emphasizing their dedication to enhancing instructional practices and student learning outcomes.

In addition, schools offered valuable opportunities for teacher development through training and seminars, enabling educators to discover and cultivate their potential, with an average score of 3.5. It highlighted their investment in professional growth and the importance of supporting their teaching staff. Schools further promote innovation and practices aimed at upgrading the quality of instruction, received an average score of 4.1, emphasizing their commitment to staying abreast of advancements in education. Moreover, schools prioritized creating a positive and conducive learning environment, scored an impressive average of 3.7, emphasizing their efforts to provide an atmosphere that nurtures student growth and success.

In Table 9, schools demonstrated a very high level of competence in student learning outcomes, with a mean score of 4.7, which implied that they performed excellently. They prioritized and excelled in fostering positive learning outcomes, as evidenced by solid agreement among respondents. Schools were highly committed to encouraging lifelong learning (4.8) and improving learner outcomes (4.7), offering abundant learning opportunities (4.6), implementing skill-enhancement programs (4.9), and supporting student-initiated activities (4.6). These findings highlighted schools' dedication to promoting holistic development, instilling a love for learning, and empowering students to succeed.

Table 9. *The Level of School Competence in terms of Continous Improvement*

<i>Student Learning Outcomes</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
Schools encourage lifelong learning among learners.	4.8	Very High
School primary goal is to improve learner's outcomes.	4.7	Very High
School provides more learning opportunities among learners.	4.6	Very High
School provides programs to improve learners cognitive, affective ad psychomotor skills.	4.9	Very High
School support student-initiated programs and activities that could improve learning outcomes.	4.6	Very High
Total	4.7	Very High

Table 10 summarized results from a study involving 82 participants, evaluating various educational indicators. The indicators assessed were School Heads Leadership, Transparency, Continuous Improvement, and Student's Learning Outcomes. The mean scores for these indicators were 4.3, 4.5, 3.7, and 4.7, respectively. These scores corresponded to descriptive frequencies indicating that School Heads Leadership and Continuous Improvement were rated "High," while Transparency and Student Learning Outcomes were rated "Very High." It suggested strong leadership, exceptional transparency, significant continuous improvement efforts, and excellent student learning outcomes in the evaluated schools.

Table 10. *Summary of the Results*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean n=82</i>	<i>Description</i>
School Heads Leadership	4.3	High

Transparency	4.5	Very High
Continous Improvement	3.7	High
Student's Learning Outcomes	4.7	Very High

3.3. The Level of Academic Performance of Learners

Table 11 presented the level of academic performance of Grade 6 learners in 7 different schools in Maitum East District. Frequency count was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Table 11. *The Level of Academic Performance of Learners*

Description	Frequency n=161	Percentage
Outstanding (90-100)	39	24
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	46	28
Satisfactory (80-84)	54	34
Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	22	14
Did Not Meet Expectations (75 and below)	0	0
Total	161	100

Data revealed that 39 or 24% of the learners achieved outstanding academic performance. This means that learners obtained an average grade of 90 to 100 percent. 46 or 28% gained a very satisfactory academic performance. This means that learners obtained an average grade of 85 to 89 percent. 54 or 34% earned a satisfactory academic performance. This means that learners obtained an average grade of 80 to 84 percent. 22 or 14% got a fairly satisfactory academic performance. This means that learners obtained an average grade of 75 to 79 percent. All of the learners met expectations.

3.4. Significant Relationship between School-Based Management Practices and School Competence

Multiple linear regression analysis determined the significant relationship between school-based management practices and school competence.

Table 12 presented that the multiple linear regression analysis showed a significant relationship between school-based management practices and school competence. It was shown by the F-value of 9880, whose significant $F=.000$; since $\text{sig } F < .05$, the relationship was significant. The value of R-square is 0.999, which implied that 99.9 percent of the variation of school competence was due to school-based management practices, particularly leadership and governance, accountability and continuous improvement, curriculum and learning, and management of resources. Specifically, leadership and governance were significantly related to school competence ($c= 0.0257$, $p= .007$).

Moreover, curriculum and learning were significantly related to school competence ($c= 0.3531$, $p= .006$). In addition, accountability and continuous improvement have a significant relationship to school competence ($c= 0.4102$, $p= .007$) since $p < .05$. Lastly, management and resources had a significant relationship to school competence ($c= 0.3907$, $p= .003$).

These results led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, a significant relationship existed between school-based management practices and school competence.

Table 12. *Significant Relationships between School-Based Management Practices and School Competence*

School-Based Management Practices	Coefficients	School Competence		Remarks
		t-value	p-value	
Leadership and Governance	0.0257	0.239	.007	Significant
Curriculum and Learning	0.3531	3.82	.006	Significant
Accountability and Continous Improvement	0.4102	3.76	.007	Significant
Management and Resources	0.0397	4.21	.003	Significant
Multiple R	0.99			
R-square	0.99			
F-value	9880		Sig F: 0.00	
Observations	161			

3.5. Significant Relationship between School-Based Management Practices and Academic Performance of Grade 6 Learners

Multiple linear regression analysis was employed to determine the significant relationship between school-based management practices and the academic performance of Grade 6 learners.

Table 8 presented that the multiple linear regression analysis showed a significant relationship between school-based management practices and learners' academic performance. It was shown by the F-value of 19.25, that it was significant $F=.000$, since $\text{sig } F < .05$. Hence, the relationship was significant. The value of R-square was 0.9058, implying that 90.58 percent of the variation in performance of the Grade 6 learners was due to the school-based management practices, particularly leadership and governance, accountability and continuous improvement, curriculum and learning, and management of resources. Specifically, leadership and governance were significantly related to school competence ($c= 0.454$, $p= .043$).

Moreover, curriculum and learning were significantly related to school competence ($c = 0.105$, $p = .008$). In addition, accountability and continuous improvement had a significant relationship to school competence ($c = 0.083$, $p = .008$) since $p < .05$. Lastly, management and resources had a significant relationship to school competence ($c = 0.465$, $p = .014$).

These results led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there was a significant relationship between school-based management practices and the academic performance of Grade 6 learners.

Table 12. *Significant Relationships between School-Based Management Practices and Academic Performance of Grade 6 Learners*

<i>School-Based Management Practices</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>School Competence</i>		<i>Remarks</i>
		<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
Leadership and Governance	.454	1.93	.043	Significant
Curriculum and Learning	.105	0.21	.008	Significant
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	.083	.171	.008	Significant
Management and Resources	.465	1.632	.014	Significant
Multiple R	0.9517			
R-square	0.9058		Sig F: 0.00	
F-value	19.25			

3.6. The Domain in School-Based Management Practices that Predicts School Competence and Academic Performance

Table 9 revealed that the domain in school-based management practices significantly predicted learners' school competence and academic performance since the probability value was $p < 0.05$. R^2 value of .625 implied that 62.5% predicted learners' school competence and academic performance, while other factors influenced the remaining 37.5%. It revealed that the t -values regarding leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, accountability, continuous improvement, and management and resources were 2.11, 3.300, 1.015, and 3.298, respectively. Therefore, the four indicators in school-based management practices, accountability and continuous improvement significantly predicted learners' school competence and academic performance. However, the best domain that significantly predicted learners' school competence and academic performance was applied performance with a coefficient of .74 and $p = .305$, which was greater than a 0.05 significance level.

Table 13. *The Domain in School-Based Management Practices that Predicts School Competence and Academic Performance*

<i>School-Based Management Practices</i>	<i>Academic Performance</i>		
	<i>B</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Leadership and Governance	.203	2.11	.003
Curriculum and Learning	.251	3.300	.004
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	0.74	1.015	.305
Management and Resources	.248	3.298	.002
R	.625		
R-square	.404		
F-value	101.01		
P-value	.000		

Discussion

The results and suggestions drawn from the data collected are presented in this chapter.

The Extent of School-Based Management Practices in terms of Curriculum and Learning, Leadership and Governance, Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and Management and Resources

The extent of school-based management was most often manifested in curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement, leadership and governance, and management and resources. In contrast, it was occasionally manifested in terms of management and resources.

The extent of school-based management practices was manifested most of the time in terms of leadership and governance. The education system had a collaborative development plan created by stakeholders and a leadership network that guided achieving shared goals. The school was structured with clear roles and responsibilities to promote shared governance. There was ongoing training for leaders and a communication network to solve learning problems. This assumption parallels the study of Brandt et al. (2019), that in the context of education, leadership and governance involved the roles and responsibilities of leaders and stakeholders in shaping and directing the education system toward its goals. It included the development of policies, programs, and initiatives that promoted learning outcomes and support the needs of students, teachers, parents, and the community. Effective leadership and governance required collaboration, communication, and shared responsibility among stakeholders to ensure the education system is responsive and relevant to the diverse needs of learners and the community.

Moreover, the extent of school-based management practices was primarily manifested in curriculum and learning. The education system prioritized the needs of all learners and the local community by localizing the curriculum and involving stakeholders in developing creative thinking and problem-solving methods. The community collaboratively monitored learning systems and continuously reviewed and improved assessment tools. The education system nurtured values and creates safe, inclusive environments for learners to become self-directed. The learning methods and resources were learner-friendly, enjoyable, and accessible, equipping learners with essential knowledge, skills, and values for their holistic growth and development.

This assumption paralleled the study of Dolev and Itzkovich (2021), claiming that curriculum and learning were interdependent and should be designed to support each other. The curriculum provided the structure and content for learning, while learning provided the opportunity for students to engage with and applied the curriculum. Effective curriculum design and learning experiences should be grounded in research-based practices, aligned with learning objectives, and responsive to the diverse needs of students. It included creating opportunities for active and authentic learning, providing feedback and assessments that supported student growth, and creating a positive and inclusive learning environment which supported student well-being and engagement.

Likewise, the extent of school-based management practices was manifested most of the time in terms of leadership and governance. The education system had a clear and agreed-upon accountability framework, which included a collaboratively developed performance system that addressed gaps through appropriate action. The community owned and continuously enhanced the accountability system to ensure responsiveness to emerging needs. Assessment criteria and tools were developed collaboratively, and participatory assessment was done regularly with the community. Assessment results and lessons learned informed feedback, as well as the technical assistance, recognition, and plan adjustment. This assumption paralleled the study of Caena and Redecker (2019), stating that effective accountability and continuous improvement processes involved the engagement of all stakeholders, including students, parents, educators, and community members. It also required multiple measures and data sources to provide a comprehensive picture of the effectiveness of educational systems and practices. Through accountability and continuous improvement processes, educational systems could ensure that the needs of students and stakeholders were met and continuously improved to provide high-quality education.

Additionally, the extent of school-based management practices mainly manifested in terms of management and resources. The education system undertook regular resource inventories and engages in accessible and inclusive planning and resource programming through a continuous dialogue with stakeholders. Resources were mobilized and managed judiciously with transparency, effectiveness, and efficiency. Resource management monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes were collaboratively developed and implemented. The network and connections that support and maintain collaborations for better resource management were managed by a system. This assumption paralleled the study of Mabborang et al. (2023), that effective management and resource allocation involved the development of clear policies and procedures for resource allocation and utilization and monitoring and evaluating resource used to ensure accountability and effectiveness. It also involved the development of systems for financial and human resource planning, recruitment, and retention to ensure an adequate and qualified workforce to support the needs of students and stakeholders.

The Level of School Competence in terms of School Heads Leadership, Transparency, Continuous Improvement, and Student Learning Outcomes

The level of school competence was very high in terms of transparency and student learning outcomes while high in terms of school heads' leadership and continuous improvement.

The level of school competence was high in terms of school heads' leadership. School leaders had a mission, vision, and goals for the school and highly assisted teachers in dealing with work problems. They highly accepted suggestions from teachers about policies and plans and established good linkages with the community. School leaders were highly focused on the excellent operation of the school. This assumption paralleled the study of Prenger et al. (2021), claiming that effective school head leadership involved creating a positive and inclusive school culture, setting high expectations for student learning, and establishing a secure and encouraging classroom environment for faculty and staff. School heads also played a critical role in managing resources, developing and implementing policies and programs, and ensuring that the school was meeting the needs of its students and stakeholders.

Also, the level of school competence regarding transparency was very high. Schools prioritize public access to relevant data and were transparent in their operations, including financial transactions. They involved stakeholders in planning and resource utilization and ensured proper auditing and liquidation of the school budget. This assumption paralleled the study of Çetin and İşçi (2022), who stated that adequate transparency in school competence involved the development and implementation of clear policies and procedures for data collection, analysis, and reporting. It also involved using multiple measures and data sources to provide a comprehensive picture of the education system's effectiveness. Through transparency in school competence, the education system could ensure that it met all learner's and stakeholders' needs and continuously improved to provide high-quality education. On the other hand, the school's competence level was high in continuous improvement. Schools framed and communicated broad goals for improvement and provided continuous improvement for the teaching-learning process. They provided opportunities very highly for teacher training and encourage innovation to upgrade quality instruction. Schools also highly prioritized creating a good learning environment that is conducive to learning. This assumption paralleled the study of Bakar and Ismail (2020), that continuous improvement involves multiple processes and practices, such as regular monitoring and evaluation of student learning outcomes, assessing the effectiveness of policies and

programs, engaging in professional development for teachers and administrators, and soliciting feedback from stakeholders.

However, the level of school competence was very high in terms of student's learning outcomes. Schools encouraged lifelong learning among learners and prioritized improving their outcomes through more learning opportunities and programs that developed cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills. Schools also highly supported student-initiated programs and activities that could improve learning outcomes. This assumption paralleled the study of Poulou et al. (2019), that practical student learning outcomes assessment required alignment with curriculum, instruction, and assessment practices and the use of evidence-based practices to support student learning and growth. It also involved using data to inform decision-making and identified areas for improvement in the education system. Through practical student learning outcomes assessment, the education system could ensure that it provided high-quality education that met the needs of all learners and stakeholders and continuously improved to meet emerging challenges and demands.

The Level of Academic Performance of Learners

The level of Grade 6 learners' academic performance was satisfactory. It indicated that learners obtained academic grades of 80 to 84 and met the expectations or requirements set by an educational institution or program. It could vary depending on the level of education, subject matter, and learning goals. However, generally, the student demonstrated a sufficient understanding of the material and skills being taught. This assumption paralleled the study of MacCann et al. (2020), who claimed that student accomplishment in various academic topics was measured by academic performance. Typically, educators used classroom performance, graduation rates, and test scores to gauge student accomplishment. Students' learning abilities, family background, peer pressure, teacher quality, and learning infrastructure all impacted their academic achievement. State and federal education authorities gathered graduation rates as a standard indicator of secondary school success. Every state administered exams to students at the elementary, middle, and high school levels each year to gauge their subject-matter ability.

Significant Relationship between School-Based Management Practices and School Competence

The analysis, as depicted in Table 7, revealed a highly significant relationship, as indicated by the F-value of 9880 with a significance level (sig F) of .000, below the typical threshold of .05. The R-square value, at 0.999, signified that a remarkable 99.9 percent of the variation in school competence could be attributed to school-based management practices, with specific emphasis on leadership and governance, accountability and continuous improvement, curriculum and learning, and resource management. Notably, leadership and governance ($c= 0.0257$, $p= .007$), curriculum and learning ($c= 0.3531$, $p= .006$), accountability and continuous improvement ($c= 0.4102$, $p= .007$), and management of resources ($c= 0.3907$, $p= .003$) all demonstrated significant individual relationships with school competence, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis and confirming a meaningful link between school-based management practices and school competence. This assumption paralleled the study of Çetin and İşçi (2022), who claimed that school-based training could enable teachers to be more flexible in their work and had a sort of commitment and adherence to the school policy and regulations. Moreover, the teacher who received school-based teacher training could assume self-development as the needs of individual teachers could be identified, investigated, and profiled. Equal opportunities were guaranteed for all the teachers in the school, and communication between administration and school teachers became easy and possible.

Significant Relationship between School-Based Management Practices and Academic Performance of Grade 6 Learners

Table 8 provided compelling evidence of a significant relationship between school-based management practices and the academic performance of Grade 6 learners. This significance was highlighted by the F-value of 19.25, with a highly significant sig F value of .000, which fell below the conventional threshold of .05, confirming the statistical significance of this relationship. The R-square value, at 0.9058, signified that a substantial 90.58 percent of the variation in the academic performance of Grade 6 learners could be attributed to school-based management practices. A correlation was found between these practices—which included leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement, and resource management—and academic success. Specifically, leadership and governance ($c= 0.454$, $p= .043$), curriculum and learning ($c= 0.105$, $p= .008$), accountability and continuous improvement ($c= 0.083$, $p= .008$), and management of resources ($c= 0.465$, $p= .014$) all demonstrated statistically significant relationships with academic performance. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected, firmly establishing a meaningful connection between school-based management practices and the academic performance of Grade 6 learners.

This assumption paralleled the study of Duru et al. (2020), that teachers significantly influenced students' academic performance. They had been given the power to oversee instruction and control all activities in the classroom. Professionalism and diligence are essential for teachers. They must be personable, listen intently, and offer answers to the issues that the children are facing. They should be well-versed in the subjects they are instructing, as well as the use of technology, contemporary, cutting-edge approaches to teaching and learning, maintaining order, and organizing all classroom and school-related activities and functions. In certain circumstances, teachers are strict, but this strictness should be kept to a minimum. The only focus of the teachers should be on improving the pupils' academic achievement and fostering their successful growth.

Conclusion

The information acquired led to the establishment of the following conclusions. First, school-based management was highly manifested most of the time in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, accountability, and continuous improvement, while

occasionally manifested in management and resources. Second, the level of school competence was very high in transparency and student learning outcomes while high in school heads' leadership and continuous improvement. Third, most Grade 6 learners obtained satisfactory academic performance. Fourth, there was a significant relationship between school-based management practices and school competence. Fifth, there was a significant relationship between school-based management practices and learners' academic performance. Lastly, there was a partial mediating role in the school-based management practices toward the school's competence and learners' academic performance.

The conclusions led to the formulation of the following suggestions. The Department of Education may provide ongoing professional development opportunities, mentorship, and coaching to ensure staff have the necessary tools to make informed decisions. Moreover, school administrators may use the results of this study as a baseline in formulating policies suited to the needs of the school community. They may invest in continuous professional development so that teachers keep them updated with the latest teaching methodologies, technology integration, and subject matter expertise. It may enhance the competence of educators and ultimately benefit the students.

Further, to address the lowest mean on management and resources, school administrators may create a collaborative improvement plan involving all stakeholders, establish effective communication channels, provide professional development, and maintain a responsive monitoring system for ongoing enhancement. Furthermore, teachers may use this study to determine educational activities for fast and efficient public service in the different schools in Maitum Districts. Teachers and other school employees may need assistance and training to acquire the abilities and know-how needed to use SBM principles successfully. The lesson plans may be reviewed and updated often to reflect the shifting demands of society and the job market. Ensure that it promotes critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and creativity. Lastly, this study may be used as a guide for future research related to school-based management practices and school competence.

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